

SITE GPR	YEAR 11	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION		STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Natural <input type="checkbox"/> Anthropic
				Min: 62.666	Max: 62.762		

In cross-section? Yes No
 In elevation drawing? Yes No
 Photos: Yes No #: 856-59
 Photo Model: Yes No #:

DEFINITION
 rocky layer to the south of SU 1390
 Covered by SU: 1412
 Fills SU:
 Filled by SU:

HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED?
 Color Composition Compaction
 FORMATION PROCESS
 Accumulation Construction Cutting Erosion Collapse Intentional deposition

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are

Anthropic <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pottery <input type="checkbox"/> Nails <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Glass	Geological <input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	Organic <input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	SOIL/MATRIX clay 10% silt 0% sand 10% <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive <table border="1"> <tr> <td>Compaction</td> <td>Color</td> </tr> <tr> <td> <input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft </td> <td> <input type="checkbox"/> Black <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) </td> </tr> </table>	Compaction	Color	<input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft	<input type="checkbox"/> Black <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)
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UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)
 Northern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit
 Southern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit previous excavation
 Western Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit
 Eastern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit
 Depth: Original Not Original

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE

Is equal to:
 Is abutted by: 1390
 Is covered by: 1412, 1446
 Is cut by: previous excavation, 1363, 1441
 Is filled by:
 Is bound to (only for masonry):
 Abuts:
 Covers: 1001
 Cuts:
 Fills:

OBSERVATIONS
 hard patch in NW corner at surface appears to be floor prep

DESCRIPTION
 Position within sector: on the southern edge of excavation in Area B, located just East of center directly south of SU 1390
 Shape: rectangular with a piece of the SE corner missing

For layers complete this section:
 Surface (slope direction: visible inclusions): even slope, western side of the SU has small rock inclusions
 Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope) no clusters
 Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): layer is thickest at South end and at North barely 2cm deep
 Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify) (bed rocks)

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (Specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

SU 1424 lay below floor prep of the room which was present at the top of this SU in the NW corner. The soil then extends down to bedrock throughout the SU, bedrock in the SE corner is cut by construction cut SU 1431
construction cuts are present on the E and West sides of the SU, but not the northern limit.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by S. Ion

Revised by CHH

PDFd by ECR

Entered by

on 21.7.2011

on 26.7.2011

on 27/7/2011

on